

Muzara'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Muzara'ah contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Muzara'ah " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Muzara'ah contract based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 4 mapping research topics surrounding Muzara'ah contracts, namely: the differences between Muzara'ah, Musaqah, and Mukhabarah contracts, Muzara'ah contracts based on the study of Islamic economic law, the influence caused by Muzara'ah contracts, and the application of Muzara'ah contracts other. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Muzara'ah contract, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Muzara'ah; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research; VOSviewer; Bibliometrics

Introduction

Contracts can be prescribed in the Islamic religion as basic behavior related to law and involving two parties. This was stated by Wahbah az-Zuhaili in his book " Al-Fiqh Al-Islami wa Adillatuhu ". Muzara'ah is a collaboration between the land owner and the cultivator, where the land owner provides the land to the cultivator and the resulting profits are shared together. Muzara'ah and mukharabah are often confused, but these two contracts have differences. The origin of the mukharabah contract comes from farmers, while the muzara'ah contract comes from land owners. Muzara'ah contract products in sharia banking in Indonesia have become superior products for sharia banks, especially as a concrete form of Islamic economic jurisprudence, because for Indonesian people, the agricultural sector is a sector that can absorb a large workforce and has a big influence on food commodities and the economy world.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Muzara'ah contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion using library research. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Muzara'ah contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Muzara'ah contract,

both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

The Muzara'ah contract is a system of cultivating someone else's land by farmers with a profit sharing system that has been agreed between the land owner and the farmer. The land owner hands over a plot of land to the farmer for cultivation, while all costs for the work and seeds are borne by the land owner. Farmers only need to prepare workers.

Islamic Financial Inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial Inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial Inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial Inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial Inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Muzara'ah contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Muzara'ah contracts on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal *Sinta* via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Muzara'ah " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping

research topics around the Muzara'ah contract based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Muzara'ah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

Search results of research publications regarding muzara'ah contracts in sharia financial institutions from 2005 to 2022 show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last five years. We obtained publication data in the form of articles totaling 43 titles originating from accredited national journals. Thus, the average scientific publication related to muzara'ah contracts is three or more articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the Muzara'ah contract by year

Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles
2005	1	2018	6
2013	1	2019	4
2014	2	2020	5
2015	2	2021	11
2016	6	2022	3
2017	2		
Total 43			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are four affiliates or institutions that publish the most journals related to muzara'ah contracts in sharia financial institutions.

Table 2. Institutions and journals that publish scientific publications regarding the Muzara'ah contract

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Al-Amwal: Journal of Islamic Economic Law, Journal of Sharia Economics, Muamalah, Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics	2
Al-Muzara'ah, Almujtamae: Journal of Community Service, Amwaluna (Journal of Sharia Economics and Finance), E-Mabis: Journal of Management and Business Economics, El-Iqthisadi, El-Iqtishod: Journal of Sharia Economics, Global Review of Islamic Economics And Business, Indonesian Journal of Business Analytics, Invest Journal of Sharia & Economic Law, Iqtishoduna: Journal of Islamic Economics, Islamic Economics Journal, J-Alif: Research Journal of Sharia Economic Law and Islamic Culture, Jesi (Indonesian Sharia Economic Journal), Journal of Islamic Monetary Economics And Finance, Al-Maslahah: Journal of Sharia Science, Journal of Sharia Economic Dynamics, Al-Musthofa: Journal of Sharia Economics, Journal of Islamic Economics and Business,	1

Journal of Indonesian Economics, Journal of Sharia Economic Law, Journal of Samudra Hukum Law, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, Mandala Education Scientific Journal (Jime), Journal of Sharia Science Integration (Jisrah), Justisia Ekonomika Journal: Master of Sharia Economic Law, Sharia Journal of Islamic Law, Al-Mustashfa: Research Journal of Sharia Economic Law, Muamalat: Journal of Sharia Economic Law Studies, Muamalatuna, Premise Law Journal, Sasi, Studia Economica: Journal of Islamic Economics.

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Each researcher wrote 1 journal article about the Muzara'ah contract. They are Muhammad Ruslan Abdullah, Dede Rohmana, Rachmat Sugeng, Nurviyanti Andang (Fajar University), Firman Muh Arif (IAIN Palopo), Ja'far Assagaf (IAIN Surakarta), Tuti Kurnia, Imam Abdul Aziz (Juanda Bogor University), Nur Rahmah, Kasmawati Kasmawati; Syamsuddin B (IAI Al-Mawaddah Warramah), Ainun, Suitra Barakah Pipin, Siti Nujul Fajri, Yulius Dharma, Ichsan, Hanif, Andika Mursada (Malekussaleh University), Ahmad Syaickhu, Nik Haryanti, Alfin Yuli Dianto (IAI Pangeran Diponegoro), Arga Satria Wisesa, Siti Inayatul Faizah, Rifaldi Majid, Dias Rizqi Wardani, Siti Inayatul Faizah (Airlangga University), M Furqan, Nur Ain Harahap, Hasanuddin Hasanuddin (Uismuh Makasar), Nur Ichsan, Ali Aminulloh, Siti Zayyini Hurun In, Nano Suyatna, Udin Komarudin (Ma'some University), Abdul Mutalib, Muhammad Ngasifudin, Abdur Rohman, Nur Cahyati (Trunojoyo Madura University Bangkalan), Dede Purnama (UIN Sultan Maulana Hasanuddin Banten), Oladokun Nafiu Olaniyi, Mohamad Asmy Bin Mohd Thas Thaker, Hassanudin Mohd Thas Thaker; Anwar Allah Pitchay (University of Malaysia), Dani El Qori (Abdullah Faqih Islamic Institute), Aldo Muhklison, Lucky Rachmawati (Surabaya State University), Muhammad Rafly, Rasiam Rasiam (IAIN Pontianak), Nini Zulhanif, Afrian Raus (IAIN Batusangkar), Ahmad Ajib Ridlwan (Surabaya State University), Baso Akib, Niluh Anik Sapitri, Riskawati, M Thahir Maloko, Rosmiyati Rosmiyati (UIN Allauddin Makasar), Muhammad Natsir, Muhammad Rafly, Siti Sahara (Ocean University), Dyah Ochtorina Susanti, A'an Efendi, Nuzulia Kumala Sari (Jember University), Iin Parlina, Achmad Otong Busthomi, Edy Setyawan (IAIN Syekh Nurjati), Zainuddin S, Eno Suhamdani, Andi Triyawan, Umrah Umrah (Al-Syariah Mandar University), Wiwin, Bello Sani Yahuza (University Bayero).

Study Mapping Research Regarding Muzara'ah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions

Article search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (research Information System) format, then input and analyzed using VOSViewer. The results are as follows:

Network visualization of research development maps regarding Muzara'ah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

The results of the network visualization on the co-word map of research developments surrounding Muzara'ah contracts in Sharia Financial Institutions are divided into 8 clusters and 100 topics, as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 18 topics, namely: agricultural product, analysis, case study, fertilizer, income, inebengi village, management, mukharabah, net income, owner, profit, profit sharing, rice production, seed, muzaraah system, tenant
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 17 topics, namely: article, benefit, concept, cooperation, country, development, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, land owner, mudaraba, muzaraah, muzaraah akad, plant, practice, rice, soybean farmer, term
- Cluster 3. Dark blue consists of 16 topics, namely: agricultural sector, agriculture, agro financing, bmt, farmer, glinggang village, impact, implementation, land, landowner, problem, search method, rice field owner, share, source, viability
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 15 topics, namely: agreement, application, collaboration, data collection technique, documentation, farm, fiqh muzaraah, interview, Islamic agreement, Marengan Laok village, observation, person, Ponorogo, research, village
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 11 topics, namely: Bandung, farm owner, farm worker, indicators, Indonesia, Islam, Islamic law, Jakarta, Lamongan, Yogyakarta, welfare
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 11 topics, namely: muzaraah contract, capital, condition, cultivator, mamminasae village, cultivator, farmer, rice field, rice fields, sharia economic law
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 8 topics, namely: agricultural land, al mukharabah, al muzaraah, contact, principle, production, production sharing, solution.
- Cluster 8. Color Chocolate consists of 4 topics, namely: business, muzaraah contact, potato farmer, welfare level.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Differences between Muzara'ah, Musaqah, and Mukhabarah Contracts

Based on a review of literature reviews in previous research journals, researchers found differences between Muzara'ah, Musaqah and Mukhabarah contracts. The main difference between the three contracts lies in the division of roles, responsibilities and results between the land owner and the party responsible for working on the land. In a Muzara'ah agreement, the land owner provides land and capital, while the cultivator provides labor and equipment. In a Musaqah agreement, the land owner provides the land, while the managing party provides labor and equipment. Meanwhile, in a Mukhabarah agreement, the land owner provides land and capital, while the cultivator provides labor and equipment.

Muzara'ah, Musaqah, and Mukhabarah contracts are types of contracts used in the context of agriculture or land management. Here are the differences between the three:

1. Muzara'ah Agreement. The Muzara'ah contract is an agreement between the land owner and the person who works on the land to carry out agricultural business. In this contract, the muzara' is responsible for providing labor, equipment and plant maintenance, while the musyarik provides land and capital. The harvest is then divided between the musyarik and muzara' according to the previous agreement.
2. Musaqah Agreement. The Musaqah agreement is an agreement between the land owner and the party responsible for irrigating and managing the land. The mustasiq is responsible for providing labor, equipment and land maintenance, while the musaqi provides the land. The harvest is divided between musaqi and mustasiq according to a previously established agreement.
3. Mukhabarah Agreement. The Mukhabarah Agreement is an agreement between the land owner and the party responsible for cultivating and managing the land. The khabir is responsible for providing labor, equipment and land maintenance, while the mukhabir provides the land and capital. In this contract, the harvest is divided between the mukhabir and khabir based on a previous agreement.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Muzara'ah Agreements Based on Islamic Economic Law Studies

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found several topics surrounding the Muzara'ah contract based on the study of Islamic economic law, including:

1. Object of the Contract: The object of the Muzara'ah contract is agricultural land owned by the first party (muzara'). This land is handed over to a second party (mustajir) to be managed and cultivated.
2. Agreement and Conditions: The Muzara'ah contract must involve an agreement between both parties, namely the muzara' (land owner) and the mustajir (farmer). The terms and conditions of the contract must be clearly stipulated in the agreement agreed to by both parties.
3. Profit Sharing: In Muzara'ah, the sharing of agricultural produce is done based on an agreement between the muzara' and the mustajir. Profit sharing can be agreed in the form of a certain percentage, where the land owner gets a fixed share or a fixed share plus a variable share of the agricultural produce.

4. Division of Responsibilities: Responsibilities related to production costs, land management and agricultural maintenance can be determined in the Muzara'ah contract. Typically, landowners are responsible for providing the land, while farmers are responsible for working, managing the land, and caring for the crops.
5. Period and Time Period: Muzara'ah contracts can be determined for a certain period or a certain season. The validity period of the contract and the distribution of profits must be clearly specified in the agreement.
6. Risks and Losses: In Muzara'ah, risks and losses related to agricultural production can be borne by the mustajir (farmer) unless caused by error or negligence on the part of the muzara' (land owner).

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence Caused by the Muzara'ah Agreement

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found several influences caused by the Muzara'ah agreement, including:

First, farmer income. This can vary depending on various factors, such as the agreements stipulated in the contract, the quality of the land, the type of crops grown, and market conditions. The following are some general effects that can occur: (1) Fair distribution of results: In a muzara'ah contract, the distribution of results between the land owner and the farmer is determined in the initial agreement. If the agreement is fair, then farmers have the potential to earn adequate income from the harvest. Balanced distribution of results can provide incentives to farmers to increase productivity and quality of agricultural products. (2) Fixed or Flexible Profit Sharing: In a muzara'ah contract, the profit sharing can be determined in a fixed form (for example, a fixed percentage of the harvest) or flexible (for example, based on an agreement after the harvest). For farmers, having flexibility in sharing results can provide the opportunity to earn greater income if harvest results exceed expectations. (3) Access to Capital and Equipment: Through muzara'ah contracts, farmers can gain access to the necessary capital and agricultural equipment. This can help farmers increase productivity and efficiency in managing land. Thus, muzara'ah contracts can potentially increase farmers' income by providing better access to resources. (4) Risk Sharing: One of the advantages of a muzara'ah contract is the sharing of risks between the land owner and the farmer. If the harvest is bad due to external factors such as weather or a plant disease outbreak, the land owner also bears the losses. In this case, farmers will not lose all their income, thereby providing financial stability. (5) Increased Skills and Knowledge: Through muzara'ah contracts, farmers can get the opportunity to learn from more experienced land owners. This collaboration can help farmers develop their skills and knowledge in better agricultural practices. By improving these skills, farmers have the potential to increase their agricultural yields and income.

Second, community welfare, namely: (1) Increased Income: Muzara'ah contracts provide farmers with the opportunity to have access to agricultural land without having to buy it. In this way, farmers who have agricultural skills can work on the land and obtain harvests that can increase their income. This has the potential to improve the standard of living of farmers and reduce poverty levels in society. (2) Increased Food Security: By using the Muzara'ah Agreement, more agricultural land can be used for food production. This means increasing agricultural production which can help meet people's food needs. In this way, the Muzara'ah Agreement can contribute to food security and reduce dependence on food imports. (3) Risk Sharing: In the Muzara'ah Agreement,

risks in agricultural businesses are mostly shared between the land owner and the farmer. Land owners do not need to worry about land management and production costs, while farmers are responsible for cultivating the land and carrying out agricultural activities. In this case, the Muzara'ah Agreement helps reduce the risk burden borne by individual farmers and can provide financial protection. (4) Agricultural Development: With the Muzara'ah Agreement, land owners who do not have agricultural skills or resources to manage their land can exploit the agricultural potential they have. This can encourage the development of the agricultural sector and increase the productivity of previously unused land. In the long term, this can bring economic and development benefits to agricultural areas.

Third, eradicate poverty. The following are some of the positive influences of the muzara'ah contract on alleviating poverty: (1) Increasing access to poor farmers: The muzara'ah contract provides poor farmers with the opportunity to access agricultural land without having to own their own land. This allows them to engage in production without having to face major financial obstacles, such as purchasing land or farming equipment. Thus, muzara'ah contracts can help reduce economic disparities and provide fairer access to agricultural resources. (2) Increased agricultural productivity: By using muzara'ah contracts, landowners who may not have the expertise or resources to manage their own agricultural land can allow skilled farmers to manage the land. Skilled and experienced farmers can increase land productivity by implementing good agricultural techniques and using the right inputs. This increase in productivity can produce larger harvests and increase the income of farmers, including those in conditions of poverty. (3) Fair distribution of the harvest: One important aspect of the muzara'ah contract is the fair distribution of the harvest between the land owner and the farmer. Typically, this share of the harvest is specified in the initial agreement, allowing farmers to get a fair share of the fruits of their labor. This provides incentives for farmers to work hard and achieve better results. In the context of alleviating poverty, fair distribution of results can help improve the income and economic conditions of poor farmers. (4) Increasing skills and knowledge: Through muzara'ah contracts, poor farmers can work directly with land owners or parties who have expertise in agriculture. This provides an opportunity for farmers to gain new skills and knowledge in agricultural land management, cultivation techniques, resource management, and so on. With these increased skills and knowledge, poor farmers can develop their own capabilities in agriculture and increase their opportunities to increase income.

Fourth, economic development of the people. The implementation of the muzara'ah contract can have several positive influences on the economic development of the people, including: (1) Increasing agricultural production: The muzara'ah contract allows the use of agricultural land that was previously not utilized optimally. By involving farmers who have expertise and experience in agriculture, agricultural production can be increased. This has the potential to increase food availability, reduce dependence on imports, and strengthen a country's food security. (2) Risk sharing: In a muzara'ah contract, business risks between the land owner and farmer are shared fairly according to the agreement. If the harvest results are poor due to natural factors, the land owner will not lose all his capital, and the farmer will not experience major losses. This creates a fairer mechanism for sharing risks and encourages more people's participation in the agricultural sector. (3) Empowerment of farmers: Through muzara'ah contracts, farmers have the opportunity to manage agricultural land

without having to have large capital. This can increase farmers' economic independence, reduce poverty and improve their standard of living. As farmers' income increases, people's purchasing power also increases, which in turn can encourage overall economic growth. (4) Local community development: Muzara'ah contracts can help develop local communities through the creation of new jobs, transfer of knowledge and skills in agriculture, and increased access to markets. This can empower local communities and support economic growth in the area.

Fifth, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The following are several ways in which Muzara'ah contracts can contribute to the SDGs: (1) Poverty Alleviation (SDG 1): Muzara'ah contracts can help alleviate poverty by providing landless farmers with the opportunity to continue participating in agricultural activities. They can use land provided by landowners to generate food and income. (2) Sustainable Food (SDG 2): Muzara'ah contracts can increase food production and agricultural sustainability. By using existing land efficiently and with the help of good agricultural techniques, Muzara'ah contracts can increase agricultural productivity and contribute to food security. (3) Health and Welfare (SDG 3): Through the Muzara'ah contract, farmers can produce healthy and nutritious food for public consumption. Thus, the Muzara'ah contract plays a role in improving the health and welfare of the population through better access to quality food. (4) Sustainable Economic Growth (SDG 8): Muzara'ah contracts can support sustainable economic growth by providing opportunities for farmers to participate in economic activities, generate income, and strengthen their livelihoods. This can also help reduce economic inequality and increase financial inclusion. (5) Ecosystem Protection (SDG 15): Muzara'ah agreements implemented with sustainability principles can promote environmentally friendly agricultural practices. By paying attention to the principles of conservation of natural resources and the environment, the Muzara'ah contract can help protect and maintain ecosystems that are important for the sustainability of our planet.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Application of Other Muzara'ah Contracts

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found other applications of the Muzara'ah contract, including:

First, at Sharia Financial Institutions. In implementing the Muzara'ah contract at Sharia Financial Institutions, the following are several general steps that can be followed: (1) Identify opportunities: Sharia Financial Institutions identify investment or financing opportunities in the agricultural or agricultural sector. This could include crops, livestock, or other agricultural activities. (2) Potential evaluation: Sharia Financial Institutions evaluate the potential and risks of agricultural projects to be financed. This evaluation involves analysis of technical, economic and financial aspects. (3) Partner selection: Sharia Financial Institutions select business partners or farmers who will collaborate in agricultural projects. This partner usually has knowledge and expertise in the agricultural sector that is appropriate to the project to be carried out. (4) Contract agreement: Sharia Financial Institutions and business partners or farmers make a Muzara'ah contract agreement. In this contract, details about the types of crops or agricultural activities to be carried out, the distribution of results, and the responsibilities of each party will be clearly regulated. (5) Financing: Sharia Financial Institutions provide financing necessary for agricultural activities, such as purchasing seeds, fertilizer, agricultural

equipment, or other operational costs. This financing usually takes the form of capital or goods handed over to business partners or farmers. (6) Project implementation: Business partners or farmers carry out agricultural activities in accordance with the contractual agreement. They are responsible for the management and care of land or livestock used in the project. (7) Sharing of results: After harvesting or selling agricultural products, the results obtained will be divided according to the agreement in the Muzara'ah contract. Usually, the results are divided between Sharia Financial Institutions as capital owners and business partners or farmers as managers. (8) Reporting and monitoring: Sharia Financial Institutions carry out reporting and monitoring regarding financed agricultural projects. This is done to ensure the project runs in accordance with the agreement and the results obtained are as expected.

Second, in the Salam-Muzara'ah linked Waqf contract. The implementation of the Muzara'ah contract in the Salam-Muzara'ah linked Waqf contract can be carried out using the following steps: (1) The party who wants to make the waqf (the waqf recipient) determines the plot of land that will be planted by the other party in the Muzara'ah contract. (2) The party receiving the waqf (seller in the Salam contract) hands over the land to the party who will carry out the Muzara'ah contract (farmer or muzari'). (3) The party carrying out the Muzara'ah contract is responsible for cultivating the land, planting plants and managing it according to the agreement with the waqf recipient. (4) After the planting period is over, the harvest will be distributed between the waqf recipient and the party carrying out the Muzara'ah contract in accordance with the agreed agreement. (5) The waqf recipient (seller in the Salam contract) uses part of the harvest received to finance waqf activities in accordance with the previously determined waqf objectives.

Third, in the agricultural, plantation, fishery and salt pond sectors. The following is an explanation of the application of the Muzara'ah contract in these sectors: (1) Agricultural Sector: In the agricultural sector, capital owners (muqarrij) can provide capital in the form of seeds, fertilizer, agricultural tools, and so on. Meanwhile, land managers (muzara') are responsible for cultivating the land, caring for plants, and carrying out other agricultural activities. The results of the agricultural business will be divided between the muqarrij and muzara' based on a previously determined agreement. (2) Plantation Sector: The application of the Muzara'ah contract in the plantation sector is similar to the agricultural sector. Muqarrij provides capital in the form of plant seeds, fertilizer, pesticides, and so on. Muzara' is responsible for caring for plants, carrying out maintenance, and harvesting plantation products. The distribution of results between the two parties is carried out in accordance with the previously agreed agreement. (3) Fisheries Sector: In the fisheries sector, muqarrij can provide capital in the form of fishing equipment such as nets, boats, and so on. Muzara' is responsible for fishing, maintaining equipment and processing the catch. The fish catch obtained will then be divided between the muqarrij and muzara' in accordance with a previously determined agreement. (4) Salt Pond Sector: In the salt pond sector, muqarrij can provide capital in the form of facilities and equipment to manage salt ponds, such as embankments, water channels, and so on. Muzara' is responsible for maintaining the pond, controlling water quality, and carrying out the salt production process. The results of salt production will then be divided between the muqarrij and muzara' in accordance with the previously agreed agreement.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 4 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding Muzara'ah contracts in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Differences between Muzara'ah, Musaqah and Mukhabarah contracts; (2) Muzara'ah Agreement based on the study of Islamic economic law; (3) The influence caused by the Muzara'ah agreement; and (4) Application of other Muzara'ah contracts.

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